
Finding Your Intercept:

The research process laid bare, life demystified or just another motivational balderdash?

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ABSTRACT

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This illustrative essay uses the analogy of the research process to explain how life works – how we can find a balance amid uncertainties. Whether you want a simplified summary of how the research process works, wish to reflect on how to manage the numerous turbulences of life, or just need some inspiration to brighten your day, this short reflection will help.

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In statistics, the *intercept* is the expected mean value of the dependent variable (Y) when all predictors (X's) are zero.¹ Sounds technical, right? Think of it this way: if you stripped away all the other factors that could possibly influence an outcome, the intercept tells you what is left. It is the baseline, the constant.

Before we get ahead of ourselves, let us back up a little and start with how we even got to the point of talking about regression analysis, which is where the idea of the intercept comes from. To make sense of it, we will take a walk through the process of research in the simplest way possible.²

Why is life full of problems?

Every research starts with a *problem* we want to solve. In life and in organisations, we are constantly surrounded by problems – big and small. Research is simply a systematic way of saying: “*Why is this happening, and what can I do about it?*”

Take a business example. Suppose you are a small business owner, and lately you have noticed that your employees are leaving your company more often than you'd like. One after another, they resign. You are worried because hiring new staff is expensive and training them takes time. So, you ask yourself: Why are they leaving? That “why” is what research tries to answer. The employees

leaving is the *effect* (the thing that happens). The reasons for leaving are the *causes*. In research language, we call the effect the *dependent variable* (because it depends on other factors), while the causes are called *independent variables* (because they are the possible reasons behind the effect).

There is no smoke without fire.

Now, here is something important: both the cause and the effect can look different from situation to situation. For example, employees in one company might leave because of poor pay, in another because of bad leadership, and in another because of lack of growth opportunities. Because these things change depending on the person, place, or situation, researchers call them *variables*. The challenge, however, is that you cannot study every possible variable at once. Life is too complex for that. Instead, researchers select a few manageable factors and focus on, while trying to hold others constant.

This is exactly what we did in our elementary science experiments. Do you remember putting one green plant in the sunlight and another in the dark cupboard, just to see the difference? We were testing one variable, sunlight, while trying to hold others (like water and soil) constant. That is the same principle researchers apply, though they sometimes make it sound too complicated.³

Ask the right questions.

Back to our employee turnover example. You can try to figure out why employees are leaving in many ways. The most direct approach would be to ask those who already left: “*Why did you leave?*” However, there is a problem with this approach. Someone who has left, perhaps angrily, might give an answer that is not the whole truth. Others may not even bother to respond.

This is why organisational psychologists prefer to study people’s *intention* to leave – that is, whether current employees are thinking about leaving—rather than waiting until they have already gone. They call this *turnover intention*. By measuring intention, you get a chance to prevent the actual turnover before it happens. Before you start, you frame a research question: *Does salary affect turnover intention?* In other words, do employees who earn more feel less like leaving?

Measure what matters.

At this point, you need to translate these big ideas into something you can *measure*. This process is called *operationalisation*. You can define remuneration (pay) as “the amount of money an employee receives monthly for doing their job.” This can be measured in naira, dollars, or placed in salary brackets. Turnover Intention, on the other hand, you can define it as “the degree to which an employee is considering leaving the organisation within the next year.” This might be measured by asking employees to respond to statements like: “*I often think about quitting my job*” on a scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

Once you have defined and measured these concepts, you are no longer talking in abstract terms. You have clear indicators you can collect data on.

Data is King.

Now comes the next big step: *data collection*. If you have 500 employees in your company, it might be unrealistic to ask all of them. That is where *sampling* comes in. You select a smaller, manageable

group, say 50 employees, that represents the whole. If you choose them wisely (randomly, across departments and job levels), their answers can give you a fairly accurate picture of the entire company.

To gather the data, you will need to use an *instrument*. This is usually a survey questionnaire. This will include questions about salary and turnover intention, along with other background information. Once employees fill it out, you collect the responses and organise them.

And bravo – you now have *data*.

So, you've collected your data. You now have salary figures from your employees, and their answers to questions about whether they are considering leaving the company. The big question is: *What do these numbers actually say?* This is important because, data by itself does not tell you much until you analyse it.

This is where *data analysis* comes in. Think of data like ingredients in your kitchen. On their own, they don't tell you much. But once you start cooking – mixing, heating, seasoning – the final meal begins to make sense. In research, the “cooking” is done through analysis, and one of the first tools we often use is correlation.

Two cannot walk together until they agree

Correlation simply tells you whether two things move together. For instance, when salary goes up, does turnover intention go down? When study hours increase, do exam scores also increase? When stress levels rise, does sleep quality fall?

Correlation gives you a number, called the correlation coefficient, or r between -1 and $+1$. A value close to $+1$ means both variables move together strongly in the same direction. (E.g., more study, higher grades). A value close to -1 means they move strongly in opposite directions. (E.g., more salary, less turnover intention). A value near 0 means there is no clear correlation between the two variables.

In our earlier example on employee turnover, if we find a correlation of -0.60 between salary and turnover intention, it means that as salary increases, turnover intention tends to decrease, and the relationship is moderately strong. This sounds interesting and useful, right? Not necessarily! This is because correlation has its limits.

That I smile with you does not mean I love you.

Here's the problem: correlation only tells you that two things move together. It does not tell you:

1. **How big the effect is.** A correlation of -0.60 tells us there is a relationship, but not *how much turnover intention changes for every unit of salary*.
2. **Which way the cause runs.** Higher salaries may reduce turnover intention, but it could also be that companies with lower turnover intention can afford to pay higher salaries. Correlation alone cannot tell you the direction of influence.
3. **What happens when you add more factors.** In real life, outcomes rarely depend on just one variable. Turnover intention may depend on salary, yes, but also on workload, leadership, or opportunities for growth. Correlation cannot handle this complexity.

That is why researchers move to a more powerful tool called *regression analysis*.

Let's connect the smoke to the fire.

If correlation is like observing that two friends often show up together, regression is like asking: "Does one friend's decision to show up influence the other, and if so, by how much?" Regression doesn't just say variables are related. It tries to quantify the relationship, estimate its strength, and allow us to make *predictions*. The simplest form of this is called linear regression, and it is expressed in this equation:

$$Y = a + bX + e$$

Don't let the symbols scare you – it is simpler than it looks. Y is the outcome we care about (e.g., turnover intention). X is the factor we think influences Y (e.g., salary). b is the slope or coefficient. It tells us how much Y changes when X changes by one unit. If $b = -0.4$, then for every extra ₦10,000 increase in salary, turnover intention decreases by 0.4 on our 1–5 scale. a is the intercept (we will come back to this soon). It tells us what Y would be if $X = 0$. e is the error term. This accounts for all the other variables we didn't include, because life can never be fully explained by just one or two factors.

Let's do some classwork.

Imagine we run the regression in software like SPSS or R. The computer processes our survey data and spits out results. It might say something like:

$$\textit{Turnover Intention} = 4.5 - 0.002 \times (\textit{Salary})$$

What does this mean? The *slope* is -0.002, which means for every ₦1,000 increase in salary, turnover intention decreases slightly. The negative sign shows the direction: more salary → less intention to leave. The *intercept* is 4.5. This means that if salary were reduced to zero, the predicted turnover intention would be 4.5 (on a scale of 1 to 5). In other words, without pay, almost everyone would want to leave. The R^2 might be 0.36, which means that salary explains 36% of the variation in turnover intention. The other 64% is due to other factors we have not included, or just random error.

This is how regression works. It does not just tell you there is a relationship. It gives you a model of how the relationship works, quantifies it, and tells you how much of the outcome can be explained by your chosen predictors.

Back to intercept.

Now let us pause and focus on the intercept – " a " in the equation. In statistics, the intercept is the *starting point*. It tells you what the outcome would be if all other variables were set to zero. It is like asking: *If nothing else is working, what is the baseline?* Think back to the plant experiment. If you deprived the plant of sunlight (our X variable), it would not just vanish into thin air. It would still have a starting point – perhaps a pale, weak form, but still a baseline of life. That baseline is the intercept.

In our salary-turnover intention example, the intercept of 4.5 tells us: even if salary is completely zero, turnover intention won't be zero—it will be very high (almost everyone would plan to leave). Why is this important? Because in life, no matter how many factors we add to explain success or

failure, there's always a constant, a starting point. Something that remains even when everything else is stripped away.

This is where statistics begins to mirror life. Life has many variables — health, economy, timing, relationships, luck. But in the midst of all these, the key question is: What is your intercept? What is the thing that remains when everything else is taken away?

We are all researchers.

In life, just like in research, we are constantly asking questions: *Why is this happening to me? What can I do to change it?* If your business fails, you ask: *Was it because of the economy, competition, or poor planning?* If a relationship doesn't work out, you ask: *Was it me, the other person, or circumstances beyond our control?* If you succeed at something, you wonder: *Was it hard work, luck, God's favour, or all of the above?*

Life is full of dependent variables (outcomes we care about), independent variables (factors that might explain them) and even mediator and moderator variables (some big words that researchers use to mean that other variables *intervene* or even *confound* their understanding of how the independent variables affect the dependent variables). Yet, just like in research, we cannot control or study every variable at once. We can only focus on a few and try to understand the patterns.

In statistics, regression is a tool for prediction. But in life, regression can also be a metaphor — a way to think about how our past, present, and future connect. Imagine your life as a line on a graph. Each event, each choice, each relationship is like a data point. Some points are high, some low, some close to the line, others far away. Your “regression line” is the story that ties all these scattered points together into a pattern.

However, here is the important part: every regression line has an intercept. The intercept is where the line crosses the vertical axis—the point where everything begins when the predictors are zero. In life, this intercept is like your starting grace, your inner anchor, or your unchanging worth. It is the value you have before anything else is added — before your achievements, before your struggles, before the influences of others.

Think of it this way: your grades may rise and fall; your career may soar or stumble; friendships may grow or fade. Yet, your intercept remains — your core identity, your God-given value, the foundation that does not depend on the predictors of success or failure.

Don't go with the slope.

In the rush of life, we often confuse the slope (how things are trending) with the intercept (who we are at the core). For example, a student might say, “I failed a test; therefore, I'm a failure.” But regression reminds us: no, the slope is just a part of the story. The intercept — your worth — remains untouched. A professional might say, “My career is going down; therefore, my life is meaningless.” Again, regression says: not true. The intercept is still there. Even when predictors (circumstances) change wildly, your line always has a starting point. You are never nothing. Finding your intercept means discovering that core truth about yourself—the place where your story begins, regardless of external variables.

What is your intercept?

Think of your own life as a dataset. What were the low points? What were the high points? Maybe there were times when you felt the points didn't even fit the line – when nothing made sense. But regression has a way of pulling the points together to reveal a pattern. When you step back, you begin to see: The challenges gave slope. The blessings gave height. But the intercept gave *grounding* – a reminder that at zero, you were still someone of value.

Perhaps your personal “intercept” is your faith, your family, your resilience, or simply the fact that you are created with worth that no predictor can erase.

A Poem to the Intercept

Let us write a poem in honour of the intercept:

*When all predictors fade away, still the line remains,
Anchored at the axis, steady through the change.
Not my rise, nor fall, define the whole of me,
My intercept reminds me: I am loved, I am free.*

If regression is about predicting an outcome based on many variables, then life itself feels like a giant regression model. So many factors feed into who we become – our family background, education, relationships, opportunities, failures, even the random events we never planned for. Yet, just like in statistics, life also has an intercept. That one thing that holds us when everything else changes.

For me, my intercept is clear. It is built on three anchors:

1. **First, God's unfailing love.** When all else fails, I know He is there for me⁴. I am sure of His promises, His mercy, and His plans for me – plans of good and not of evil⁵. Even when life feels unfair, I know that somehow, He is weaving it all into something good⁶.
2. **Second, the journey He has taken me through.** The experiences I have had, the lessons I have learned, and the training He has walked me through have shaped me into someone who cannot be easily pushed aside. At the time, I didn't like it – like a child being disciplined, I wanted comfort, not chastening. But today, I see the strength it built in me. Today, if you dropped me in Kafanchan or Tokyo with nothing – no money, no capital, no connections – I know I can easily stand on my feet because I have been equipped with skills, resilience, and a cross-cultural capital that makes me adaptable and ambidextrous.
3. **Third, I trust in my end.** Beyond all the ups and downs of this life, I hold on to the promise of eternity with Christ. He has guaranteed me a “happily ever after,” and that keeps me steady. It gives me perspective: whatever I go through here is temporary.⁷

These are my intercepts.

And I needed them, especially this past year. In the last twelve months, I have faced probably the harshest turbulence of my life. I have lost friends, businesses, money, and connections. I have watched dreams fall apart and doors I thought were open suddenly close. It has been a season of stripping and shaking.

But here is the miracle: in all of this, I have not lost my faith, my joy, my purpose, or myself because I have an anchor. My life is not floating aimlessly, nor am I defined by the variables that rise and fall around me. My intercept keeps me grounded.

That is why this old hymn by Priscilla Jane Owens⁸ means so much to me:

*Will your anchor hold in the storms of life,
When the clouds unfold their wings of strife?
When the strong tides lift, and the cables strain,
Will your anchor drift, or firm remain?*

*We have an anchor that keeps the soul
Steadfast and sure while the billows roll,
Fastened to the Rock which cannot move,
Grounded firm and deep in the Savior's love.*

NOTES

¹ For a detailed and technical discussion on how to interpret regression analysis, read Guthery, F. S., & Bingham, R. L. (2007). A primer on interpreting regression models. *The journal of wildlife management*, 71(3), 684-692.

² If you are a student trying to learn everything about the research process in the most simplified form, this article will help you: Nenty, H. J. (2009). Writing a quantitative research thesis. *International Journal of Educational Sciences*, 1(1), 19-32.

³ I am in no way trying to make light of the research process. For a clear discussion of why research needs to be rigorous and systematic, read the opening section of Chapter 14 of Haralambos, M., & Holborn, M. (2013). *Sociology: Themes and perspectives* (8th ed.). Collins Educational.

⁴ A systematic review of 444 quantitative studies (1962-2010) found that religious or spiritual involvement was associated with less depression in the majority of studies. Additionally, methodologically stronger studies (rated 7/10 or higher) tended to report even greater protective effects from religiosity. Read more here: Bonelli, R., Dew, R. E., Koenig, H. G., Rosmarin, D. H., & Vasegh, S. (2012). Religious and spiritual factors in depression: review and integration of the research. *Depression Research and Treatment*, 2012(1), 962860.

⁵ "This is God's Word on the subject: '...I know what I'm doing. I have it all planned out—plans to take care of you, not abandon you, plans to give you the future you hope for.'" (Jeremiah 29:11, MSG)

⁶ "And we know [with great confidence] that God [who is deeply concerned about us] causes all things to work together [as a plan] for good for those who love God, to those who are called according to His plan and purpose." (Romans 8:28, AMP)

⁷ "For our present troubles are small and won't last very long. Yet they produce for us a glory that vastly outweighs them and will last forever! So we don't look at the troubles we can see now; rather, we fix our gaze on things that cannot be seen. For the things we see now will soon be gone, but the things we cannot see will last forever." (2 Corinthians 4:17-18, NLT)

⁸ Owens, P. J. (1882). Will your anchor hold [Hymn]. In W. J. Kirkpatrick (Composer), *Songs of triumph*. Philadelphia: John J. Hood.

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